

Fig. S5A

Fig. S5A. Morphometric PCA plot 2 of informative fruiting traits (n=8). Broad-scale analysis of 257 plants of *C. howellii* (purple triangles), putative *C. howellii* (downward lavender triangles), and *C. quamash* ssp. *breviflora* (blue circles), for 14 sites. Note the variability and outliers for climatic transition zone CCT in the Columbia River Gorge. Plot 2 has same traits without CCT. Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table 1, Fig. 2 map.

Fig. S5B

Fig. S5B. Morphometric PCA plot 2 of informative fruiting traits ($n=8$; $PC1-2=62\%$). Broad-scale paired analysis of 235 plants of *C. howellii* (purple triangles), putative *C. howellii* (downward lavender triangles), and *C. quamash* ssp. *breviflora* (blue circles), for 13 sites without west-east transition zone CCT. Plot 1 includes all 14 sites. Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table 1, Fig. 2 map.